

Immersive experiences to communicate sky heritage and dark skies

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Our relationship to the sky is complex and encompasses heritage interpretation, protecting environments and the dark skies agenda. Creating transformative experiences that communicate the emotional values that underpin this relationship often proves difficult. In particular, the qualities that make heritage sites excellent places to immerse oneself in its skyscape – at-risk or remote locations – limit the number of people who can experience it. Knowledge exchange between practitioners working at these sites and the public is essential for all stakeholders involved in astronomy communication as this fosters a wider understanding and appreciation of the cosmos.

This project aims to empower astronomy communicators of the future to connect the public to the rich culture and heritage of skylscapes. Based on King Arthur's Hall on Bodmin Moor, Cornwall, United Kingdom, this case study outlines how we created and evaluated tailor-made immersive public engagement activities of cultural heritage sites. This project is grounded in the theoretical frameworks of Skylscapes and transformative learning. We introduce the heritage site and unpack the resource development for a mobile planetarium. This includes a 3D visualisation of the real sky that uses data from light pollution, 3D scanning, landscape surveying and phenomenology. We present feedback from our activities that illustrates the extent to which the project had an impact and the potential for future opportunities. Overall, the co-created resources offered the opportunity to virtually connect to the heritage sites and communicate their skylscapes.

Introduction

Our project created a unique virtual planetarium environment in tandem with outdoor learning to explore the sky experience at a heritage site at risk on Bodmin Moor, Cornwall, United Kingdom. To achieve this immersive and transformative learning experience in both a virtual and real site, we established a collaboration between science communicators, researchers and undergraduates at Nottingham Trent University (NTU), the local council, and the local community.

Each stakeholder had their own goals that we aimed to achieve. The researchers at NTU wanted to understand how the surrounding landscape and sky might have informed the site's creation. They also were interested in exploring how stars and constellations are used to tell stories and explore sites through different lenses. The undergraduate students sought to gain real-world applications of the knowledge gathered during their studies. The local council, the Cornwall National Landscapes, was interested in enhancing the connection to the site and surrounding area. The science communicators were interested in developing their skills in virtually representing landscapes in planetarium software. Finally, the local community wanted to hear more about and understand the site.

Such a diverse working group offered the insight necessary to design and co-create a meaningful virtual planetarium environment, including sounds and on-site activities that speak to all and are grounded in research and place. Vivality, it ensured the programme was deeply embedded in everyone's emotional ties to the site, including the potential audience.

Our work is based upon a conceptual framework (Brown 2013a; Brown 2013b) that draws on a deeper interpretation of the sky expressed in the term skylscapes, all seen through the lens of knowledge exchange. When virtual sites are included, this framework leads to more effective transformative learning since theoretical scenarios can be explored and worldviews can be imagined, pushing the viewer into a

liminal zone vital for transformative learning (Brown *et al.*, 2013).

Skylscapes

The term "astronomy," particularly when communicating astronomy and understanding the connection between people, society and astronomy, is biased by a modern Western viewpoint. To enable more impactful and emotionally powerful activities, we use and support the concept of skylscapes throughout our work.

Silva (2024) discussed *skylscapes* as a bias-free term for broader sky exploration that goes beyond astronomy to include anthropology, mythology, psychology, and more. It embraces a rich and deep interpretation without gross generalisations and is reflective and self-critical, ensuring continued questioning. Further, it supports many worldviews beyond simply acknowledging multiple interpretations.

Scholars have argued that one can explore a skyscape experience when fully realising that sky, land, and people interact at a site (e.g., Brown, 2013b). This can be expressed through a dialectic landscape (*Ibid*, 2013b) that simultaneously presents key factors and components, allowing the viewer to negotiate meaning and develop their own emotional connection and moment of realisation.

Transformative learning and virtual sites

We worked with the general public, predominantly adults and undergraduates, during our project. Our audiences have already been exposed to a range of pre-

existing experiences that we can mobilise for our work, leading us to engage with a more transformative learning approach (Mezirow, 2018). To empower this approach further, we include critical pedagogies and embrace a sense of being that is vital to grounding our participants and triggering an emotional response. Gruenewald (2008), who merged critical pedagogy and place-based education for his environmental work, inspired this inclusion of place. While exploring this approach for astronomy communication, specifically dark sky education involving outdoor learning at heritage sites combined with planetarium shows, Brown (2015) specifies three phases in which such transformative learning takes place, echoing the rites of passage (Bell, 2003; Van Gennep, 2019): separation, transition in a liminal space, and reintegration.

Brown's work shows how exploring through walking a landscape under low light or at nighttime, referred to here as nighttime walks, in combination with an appropriate landscape in a planetarium can achieve these phases (see examples in Figure 1). They are separated from the present day by transporting visitors through time in the planetarium, followed by experiencing familiar landscapes at night that make the familiar strange and liminal. Through guided landscape tours, planetarians can use history to engage participants with time and ultimately mobilise emotions (Brown et al. 2013). The first two main phases, when well aligned, are successful when they, as described above, transport participants from the familiar to a liminal place that emotionally connects them with the environment and sky, thereby capturing the sublime (Brown 2013a). Here, the sublime can be seen as Kant's mathematical sublime in which the viewer sees infinity in (deep-)time and (cosmological-)scale that acts as an incomprehensible chasm in which they peer while safely rooted through their emotional connection with their place. Place here is understood in the Heideggerian way (Critchley et al., 2008) with its role in skyscape enabling the viewers defined human existence, or Dasein, to explore what it means to be.

Such interactions can extend to the virtual domain to enhance engagement and offer more liminality and expansive experiences of time, resulting in a heightened emotional connection. All of these require creating immersive experiences that are surrounding, multisensory and vivid (Zhang, 2020).

Figure 1: An illustration of various innovative ways the authors have engaged participants using tools such as Stellarium and explored the Skyscape.

However, we cannot lose focus of the real physical site and move only to a virtual domain. When reflecting on any visit to a site, there is no actual pure (physical) site or (virtual) non-site. For example, even if you visit a site in person, you typically choose where to go or what interests you by using virtual resources or maps. Land artists have explored this site versus non-site (or, in our case, physical versus virtual) dialectic, allowing for negotiation of its meaning (Hobbs 1981; Flam 1996). For planetarium programs, virtual landscapes are important to ground one's viewpoint, but could they support the negotiation of meaning? This question led to developing a Stellarium landscape based on the James Turrell

Skyscape "Deershelter" installation. This landscape goes beyond simple photo-realism and captures the viewers' emotional connections and experiences (see centre left in Figure 1; Harty et al., 2019). Such more meaningful planetarium landscapes offer closer emotional attachment and generate a sublime experience.

All the above conceptual frameworks and resultant approaches require a deep, subjective, and emotional engagement with a site. Methods to achieve this are related to psycho-geography (e.g., Coverley, 2018) and landscape phenomenology (e.g., Tilley, 1994), which require walking sites repeatedly and holistically.

Knowledge exchange

To acknowledge all points of view and enable the negotiation of meaning, we worked within our institute's Knowledge Exchange (KE) Practice framework (Johnson, 2022). This approach ensures skills and knowledge are shared amongst many stakeholders, which differs from research that seeks to create new knowledge.

Our project included the following participants who collaborated and co-created our outputs: outreach practitioners, Nottingham Trent University researchers (astronomy and computing), local communities, a local council (Cornwall National Landscapes, formerly the Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty Cornwall) who manage the site and wish to see it removed from the Heritage England at Risk register, Mayes Creative who actively engage with arts communities seeking to diversify and make access to science and heritage more accessible through the arts and NTU undergraduate students. We ensured that several undergraduate students at different times in the project shared their specialist knowledge across the wider team. The undergraduates experienced real-world working scenarios, showcasing current technological advancements and offering valuable reflections on audience engagement.

The case of King Arthur's Hall

For our work, we chose King Arthur's Hall (hereafter KAH; Historic Environment Record No. 1967; Scheduled Monument CO81, Location SX1297764), a monument located in a remote part of Northwest Bodmin Moor, Cornwall (Figure 2). It is an enigmatic, banked, rectangular stone structure measuring approximately 20 meters by 47 meters. Within the bank are 56 substantial upright granite slabs. The monument dates back to the late Neolithic – early Bronze Age (around 2500-1500 BCE) or the Early Medieval period.

The purpose and exact origins of KAH remain unclear. Part of the wider project was an archaeological investigation into the Hall with Optically stimulated luminescence (OSL) and pollen dating; these results are still outstanding. Dudley (1953) believed it might have been a ceremonial site or a communal gathering place, possibly related to ritual activities, while others suggest it could have served as a prehistoric cattle enclosure.

Figure 2: The top image gives an impression of the view over King Arthur's Hall towards the Northeast, noting the different vegetation and boggy central area. Images at the bottom left and bottom centre show the location of King Arthur's Hall. Note that Bodmin Moor is designated as a dark sky landscape. The bottom right image gives an archaeological site plan by Johnson & Rose (1994) indicating the apparent North-South alignment and the location of our panoramic landscape. Image Credit: Bottom left and centre: Google Maps; Bottom right: Johnson & Rose (1994)

The remote location in a boggy area of the Moor belies the historic positioning, and it is in an area rich in megalithic monuments, which has seen extensive human activity (Barnett 1982; Johnson & Rose 1994). The location currently benefits from DarkSky International-designated dark skies and is part of the Bodmin Moor Dark Sky Park.

Because of its enigmatic nature, folkloric name, and seemingly remote location, the Hall has sparked strong perceptions about its purpose and character (e.g., Kennett, 2022). The work described here provides a unique opportunity to delve into these perceptions through innovative and immersive experiences.

Activities

The immersive experience around KAH was developed to create meaningful and deep experiences within an immersive

planetarium show and on-site. The process took place in three stages: May for survey work on-site, July to share our first draft planetarium show and co-create additional resources, and September to run the final planetarium event and tours.

Digital scanning and modelling

We chose Stellarium to deliver our planetarium show because it is free and easily accessible. Stellarium Version 24.2 supports various capabilities suited to this project: a photorealistic landscape, a light pollution layer, and a 3D landscape and movement within it. A site visit that included all stakeholders working together was required to develop these resources.

Our team used LIDAR data and archaeological mapping details from an archaeological survey by Johnson and Rose (1994), and higher-resolution data was created on-site using a mobile Arctec Eva 3D scanner.

A realistic landscape was created using DSLR imagery captured from a daytime station at one corner of the site to visualise its apparent North-South alignment (Figure 2). To ensure the horizon was precisely oriented, we used an optomechanical theodolite survey from the same site with solar azimuths to determine the true North. The result was an arcminute-precision horizon that was then imported into Stellarium (Figure 3).

In the lead-up to the trip, the NTU team, including two staff members and two students, trained together through developing a workflow, surveying and scanning very accessible small structures on our university campus and then moving to a harder-to-reach standing stone close to Nottingham. This ensured students developed a sense of ownership of the later

site survey (3D scanning – Figure 4). While onsite, the local outreach practitioners were trained in using survey equipment (see survey training – Figure 4) and advanced work in Stellarium. Local community groups shared their experiences of the site that surprisingly included the presence of water and a proposed spring on the site which we had not considered beforehand.

Light pollution survey

We generated a light pollution layer in Stellarium, vital to show the shift in time from prehistoric times to the present day. It only needed to capture the lights of the neighbouring villages, and therefore, did not require high precision.

A new station was set up close to the daytime station. Images were captured on a nearly cloudless night around midnight

when the Moon had not yet risen (light pollution survey – Figure 4). Four images were captured with a DSLR camera equipped with a fisheye lens. The images were stitched together and oriented using distant markers (top half of Figure 3).

Stellar markers were used to navigate in near darkness to KAH during nighttime to support a place-conscious experience for an alternative experience of the site. Our presence disturbed a local herd of horses not normally present during the daytime, triggering an invisible stampede only perceived through sound. Such a triggered event is a key example of how vital it is to walk a site under varied conditions or at night to capture a range of emotional responses (see Section 1.2. linked to psycho-geography and landscape phenomenology). This memory especially remained with us as an evocative experience likened to the “Wild Hunt” (a folklore theme in Western and Eastern Europe linked to mythological figures and spirits in a pursuit commonly whisking away the viewer’s soul) and included later in the planetarium show.

Scripting and co-creating a planetarium Show

Work was carried out with a new student who continued the survey work of previous students into the design of an immersive show that captured the goals of all stakeholders involved. This meaningful show is a vital step to allow the participants to explore the sublime on-site.

Landscape phenomenological work showed that approaching the site from the South made it appear as though it sat along the horizon. We started the animation along this path to capitalise on this optical illusion. Since local groups mentioned the importance of water on site we ensured to capture different sounds while walking to represent the change of vegetation (grass, moss, or dry reeds) as well as ground conditions (dry or boggy) due to water.

These aspects shaped a Stellarium video and audio virtual walk into the site: the viewer approaches through a grassy landscape, enters the site through dried rustling reeds, and finishes in the centre, where the ground remains boggy and squelchy. Added sounds included the song of skylarks recorded on site. Time is sped up, such that the viewer starts the walk before sunset and

Figure 3: A fisheye projection of the developed Stellarium landscape given our detailed survey work on site. Top: The 3D-modelled landscape, including the light pollution layer. Note the presence of the Bodmin settlement in the South-West. Bottom: The arcminute precise daytime landscape with one embankment illustrating the apparent North-South alignment. Image Credits: Stellarium

arrives as night has fully settled, adding the striking “Wild Hunt” audio.

The full immersive planetarium show begins with the above video to discuss the emotional responses of participants prompted by us in the planetarium after the “Wild Hunt” while sharing impressions. After removing the light pollution layer, we display Western and Indigenous constellations. Participants then create their own constellations by sketching them on already prepared feedback leaflets that included bright stars in the area of Orion. This activity gave them time to engage further and think about how constellations and their meanings reflect the people who created them. To highlight the apparent North-South alignment of KAH, the audience learns about methods for finding true North, including the Indian Circle Method, one of the oldest and most reliable methods for determining the cardinal directions, likely used during the Bronze Age (Brown *et al.*, 2011). This topic is further deepened by discussing how participants found our event or navigated. It is followed by a discussion of how this would change through time and if visitors realise the moving positions of sunrise or sunset on the horizon. The impact of precession is illustrated through the sped-up daily apparent rotation of the stars shown for a few select periods of time, finishing at the Bronze Age (2,000 BCE in Cornwall). The planetarium show closes with visitors being asked to imagine why the site was created but without stressing any particular interpretation. This question is intended to resonate with participants while they leave the planetarium and join our guided walk; it attempts to encourage the participants to remain open for a range of interpretations, be able to negotiate meaning, and engage with the skyscape freely.

Co-creation included using participants’ constellations as activity prompts in the show, allowing for place-based starlore (local starlore – Figure 4). The kangaroo constellation represents the recently escaped kangaroos roaming parts of Cornwall for some time. Furthermore, a dung beetle constellation was included, showing the recent knowledge gained by a visitor about the animals’ environmental importance on site. In addition, participants requested a clearer birds-eye view of the site, which was included at the start using simulated drone footage and associated

sounds. The contrast between a simple static drone’s birds-eye view and an actual human moving through the landscape has stressed the importance of walking to the site. This very useful demonstration was solely the result of participants’ co-creation and was not initially part of our show.

Guided landscape walks

Post-planetarium outdoor guided walks served as an extension of the indoor show (guided walks – Figure 4), allowing participants to transition from virtual experiences to real-world exploration. The shift from virtual to tangible provided a unique opportunity to enhance learning in a more personal yet guided setting. Through conversation and connection during the walk, participants gained deeper insights into the natural environment and its history. This experience made the exploration more meaningful and deepened their appreciation of the changing skylscapes and landscapes. The evening concluded with guided stargazing hosted in collaboration with the local astronomical community. This event allowed the local community and heritage

stakeholders to connect with the site in a new way, engaging with the Hall and the night sky in a shared, immersive experience.

Camera workshops

Additionally, we organised on-site camera workshops for local community film artists to explore the interplay of light within the natural environment. This art-science participatory element extended the reach and brought diversity to the project. Art catalysed reflective conversations, offering a unique opportunity to engage with hard-to-reach segments of the community who might not typically connect with heritage or astronomy (Liggett, 2020).

Participants engaged in slow, analogue processes using Super 8 movie film and 120 pinhole cameras. They developed their film on-site using Caffanol techniques, an example of which is shown in the camera workshop panel in Figure 4. These workshops fostered group discussions and encouraged openness, allowing artists to share techniques, inspire each other, and learn collaboratively. The results of their

Figure 4: Examples of the various aspects of the project. From top left clockwise: Local outreach practitioners supporting the horizon theodolite survey; guided walks exploring the landscape around King Arthur’s Hall; pinhole camera images captured during camera workshop; Nottingham Trent University students scanning the stones at King Arthur’s Hall; co-created constellations capturing local knowledge; and light pollution survey at King Arthur’s Hall.

workshops will be used as interpretative outputs at future KAH planetarium shows.

Project impact

Data collection and analysis

Engagement during the event was measured through a structured feedback form that participants filled out when entering and exiting the planetarium show to gain insights into the change in perceptions before and after the activity. Additionally, there were informal feedback opportunities on the walk and after the shows. The formal feedback form was divided into five sections:

1. Associations with King Arthur's Hall Before the Event: Participants were asked to share their initial thoughts and connections to the site.
2. Draw a Constellation on the Star Map: This interactive activity engaged participants with the event's astronomical theme by asking them to draw an imagined constellation using the star patterns in the sky.
3. Associations with King Arthur's Hall After the Event: This section aimed to gauge how the event influenced their perceptions of the site.
4. Rating Satisfaction with the Show and Perceived Change in View of the Site: Participants rated their enjoyment of the show and indicated whether their perception of the site had changed.
5. Other Comments: An open-ended section that allowed participants to provide additional feedback.

Feedback from 44 adult and children participants living in the local area was collected and analysed quantitatively and qualitatively. Quantitative analysis focused on the numerical ratings (e.g., levels of agreement with statements), while qualitative analysis categorised and compared participants' descriptive responses before and after the event.

Results

The event was overwhelmingly well-received, with all respondents either "agreeing" or "strongly agreeing" that they enjoyed the experience and no negative feedback. One respondent, familiar with the site, had a positive emotional response, describing the experience as moving. Common descriptors like "great" and "interesting" indicated high

participant satisfaction, showing the event effectively entertained the audience. While most participants (30 out of 44) reported some change in their perception of the site, with a shift in focus from nature and memories to astronomy, expanding participants' views of the site (Figure 5). Overall, the event successfully reinforced and slightly broadened the audience's understanding of the site.

The stakeholders had varied goals throughout the project. The KAH project's impact on the Cornwall National Landscapes was significant but nuanced. The main goal of fostering a stronger connection between people and the site was achieved, though in a complex way. In addition, a long-lasting relationship has developed with the Cornwall National Landscapes. In conjunction with outdoor learning, such immersive planetarium shows are used to communicate the findings of the wider projects related to

our work. Individuals from Mayes Creative have also used their skills to create their own landscapes to implement them into Stellarium and use them to communicate findings of other sites in Cornwall. Several NTU undergraduates have already used the real-world project to inform their final year project choices (modelling local heritage sites or communicating science) and have completed them. Especially one local group (Time-seekers) that was heavily involved in giving us their personal experiences of the site (and highlighting the theme of water) included one member who was brought to tears during our planetarium show, illustrating the substantial emotional impact we managed to evoke. Furthermore, many participants already had strong personal ties to the site, from childhood memories to frequent visits. Rather than creating new connections, the project deepened existing ones. Participants' enjoyment and the knowledge gained will likely support ongoing

Figure 5: Word cloud visualisations using three-word associations of participants in the immersive planetarium show pre-and post-event. These are prompted by asking to describe the relationship with King Arthur's Hall. The top shows words related to nature, and the bottom shows words related to questioning one's understanding.

preservation, aligning with the Cornwall National Landscapes's objective to enhance local environmental connections. Directly due to the wider project, KAH has been removed from the Heritage England at-risk register.

Project legacy and future

The KAH project achieved several key milestones. It deepened participants' and leaders' attachment to the site by encouraging them to view the sky as part of the environment, enriching their appreciation of the landscape. Positive feedback from the local council given in a post-event meeting opens the door for legacy funding to support future initiatives. The collaboration with Cornwall National Landscape and Mayes Creative also laid the groundwork for ongoing partnerships, including cross-cultural astronomy projects with which National Landscapes Cornwall and Mayes Creative have longstanding links.

Conclusions

The KAH project demonstrated the potential of heritage sites to engage audiences and foster transformative learning experiences about the intricate relationship between humans, the sky, and the land. This is especially significant, as it uses extensively a holistic approach of working on-site, exploring the phenomenology of the place, and capturing the sublime. It goes beyond a photorealistic representation of the physical environment with some stars. The KAH project has managed to support and capture the deep engagement with the site, the sky and the people and thereby evidences the importance of including the sky as part of the environment in line with the author's interpretation of skyscape. By utilising virtual planetarium environments alongside outdoor onsite activities, the project successfully captured the essence of skylscapes at heritage sites, including those at risk or in remote locations, through a combination of interdisciplinary work and landscape phenomenology. Moreover, the project's impact was greatly enhanced by its emphasis on knowledge exchange and co-creation with local stakeholders and undergraduate students, highlighting the value of collaborative approaches in educational and heritage initiatives.

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